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Comparison the Course Books Used in Teaching Turkish and English as a Foreign Language in Terms of Culture Transmission

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Abstract

Foreign language teaching is not only the teaching of the grammar and vocabulary and the acquisition of basic language skills of the target language, but it is also the teaching of the culture of the target language. Because foreign language always brings it with a foreign culture. It is extremely important that individuals learn the cultural characteristics of the country when they are learning its language for a better understanding of language. It is an undeniable fact that language and culture cannot be separated and culture must also be learnt when learning a language. Because of the perfect relation between language and culture, teaching a language also means teaching of the culture. In today's foreign language teaching, it is observed that the transmission of the culture is very important. Foreign language course books reflect the characteristics of the society that speaks the language in question, and that acts as the carrier of the culture. The role and importance of the course books used in teaching Turkish and English as foreign languages were questioned in this study, and the Gazi Turkish Teaching Set for Foreigners for A1-A2, B1-B2 levels and the New Headway Beginner, Elementary, Pre-Intermediate, Intermediate course books were analyzed and evaluated according to certain criteria. As a result of the analyses and evaluations, it was observed that Gazi Turkish Teaching Set course books included more elements of the Turkish culture, and New Headway course books included mostly universal cultural elements. In conclusion, it is possible to claim that there is not a balanced distribution between the local cultural elements and universal cultural elements in the course books prepared by the Turkish and English authors; and for this reason, these course books have missing points in the acquisition process of the cultural awareness by students.

Keywords: Cultural Transmission, Foreign Language Teaching, Course Books

1. Introduction

Though the people define culture differently, it is possible to describe its general terms with common definitions. For instance, Kongar (1999: 19) has specified for culture that it is everything produced by human beings in

addition to those created by Allah and formed by nature. According to Peck (1998), culture is all of the accepted and arranged behaviors of individuals. Upon this definition, it could be said that culture is the set of values binding a group of people and separating them from others. Holiday, Hyde, and Kullman (2004: 59) have seen culture as a complex structure formed by the belief, art, ethics, law and traditions as a whole obtained in society. All these definitions show that culture is the total of the stuff like all kinds of productions (tools, appliances, foods etc.), traditions and behavior ways etc. belonging to a certain group of people and not emerging in natural ways. Two important elements come to the forefront here. The first one is that culture is not a gift of nature, but a product of human beings. The second one is that it belongs to a group of people (nation). However; there could also be issues being beyond this group and being valid for everyone; this situation is called universal culture. Universal culture is the common share of humanity.

Talking about culture is talking about human action, human activities and human production in absolute meaning. Culture is a structure which is not natural, not existent in a ready state, produced and formed later on (Alver, ? : 14.). Therefore, it draws the attention of other people. People wonder and want to learn what other people produce. EU being aware of this has supported cultural teaching, intercultural exchange and multiculturalism in its language teaching programs with the policies they develop. The concept of culture taking its place in the language teaching programs also together with the impact of European common language criteria has an important function especially in the area of foreign language teaching; because, an individual learning a foreign language should know how the owners of that language live, what they produce and what they value to be able to comprehend the language in a healthier way. This definition means that the individuals learning a new language meet another culture other than theirs. The individual realizes the existence of another culture other than his/her culture. This gives him/her the opportunity of making a comparison between the cultures and developing different viewpoints by becoming aware of his/her own culture (İşci, 2012: 33).

Another reason for the foreign language learners to be obliged to learn the culture of the target language is the inseparable bond between language and culture. Individuals cannot decode the codes of the language as long as they cannot realize and comprehend this bond between them. According to Kramsch (1993), foreign language/second language learner should definitely learn the culture of the target language; because, he thinks that language cannot be learnt without learning the cultural context. In the same way, Byram and Morgan (1994) assert that cultural teaching is an inseparable part of language learning. For this reason; it is obligatory for the students to be aware of the differences between their own cultures and the culture of the target language. Teacher should also consider culture as an inseparable part of language teaching and handle the subject of culture in language classes. S/he should find ways for teaching culture and design experiences that will facilitate cultural learning for students. For this, teachers should find/develop materials and conduct activities for cultural teaching (İşcan, 2017: 31).

1.1 Course Books of Foreign Language Teaching and Cultural Transmission

According to Cortazzi Jin (1999), the course books used in foreign language teaching could undertake different tasks; they could be a teacher, a guide, a resource, a tutor and an authority. There are many alternative teaching materials today and course books continue to be an integral part of language learning in classroom environment. These materials are also one of the most important elements of cultural transmission. Especially when there is still no official program for teaching Turkish as a foreign language, the importance of books increases again. These books both undertake the function of being a schedule and a teaching material.

Questioning how the course books tightly held by teachers depending on their professional experiences and confidences are prepared in terms of principles is important in terms of being able to determine the success of the book, reach a better one and increase the efficiency of the lesson (Yılmaz and Esen, 2016: 85). These books should not be prepared only for grammar teaching. They should also transmit the cultural concepts within the frame of life – experience areas as well as gaining language skills and grammar rules. The course books best for purpose are those based on target and international culture among the course books that could base the cultural transmission on the source language, target language and international cultures; because, thanks to these course

books, both the convenient living patterns in the culture of the learnt language are transmitted and the cultural variety in the world is reflected (Özışık, 2004).

1.2. Criteria for the Assessment of the Cultural Elements in Course Books Used in Foreign Language Teaching

According to Kılıçkaya (2004), there are also subjects necessary to be checked while examining the cultural content in the course books in addition to the needs of students and the role of teachers. Every course book has a program peculiar to itself. This implicit program may contain socio-cultural factors, generalizations and clichés. This may slow down the development in intercultural communication. For this, the transmission of the cultural elements should be ensured by taking the viewpoints, perceptions and needs of students into consideration.

Within this context; it is necessary to determine some criteria while examining the cultural elements in course books.

National Program of England emphasizes in the cultural awareness part that students should have knowledge about various states and their cultures, compare the culture of the target language to their own cultures and make speaking exercises with native speakers (Qualification and Curriculum, 1999). Okur and Keskin (2013) have examined the cultural elements in the course books of teaching Turkish as foreign language under 7 main headings (daily life; interpersonal relations; values and education; literature, art and music; traditions and folklore; social life; geography and place). Their assessment table has also been taken as the basis for this examination.

2. Method

The data for this study were obtained from the document analysis of the books used for teaching English and Turkish as a foreign language. Document review is the analysis of all kinds of official or private written material that provides information about a subject under investigation (Creswell, 2012; Şimşek & Yıldırım, 2011). The books examined are the A1-A2, B1-B2 books of Gazi Turkish Teaching Set for Foreigners for teaching Turkish as a foreign language, and the textbooks named New Headway Beginner, Elementary, Pre-Intermediate, Intermediate for English. These books were determined using the simple random sampling method. The findings obtained from the books are handled with a theme analysis perspective. According to this analysis method, documents are divided into categories and sub-themes under the upper themes. In a sense, the subject, category and sub-themes related to the phenomenon studied in the documents are determined. In addition, the frequency and percentages related to this scoreboard table can be given.

2.1. Subject Characteristics

The study is limited with the Gazi Turkish Teaching Set for Foreigners A1-A2, B1-B2 Level course books used as course books in Teaching Turkish to Foreigners Centers of many universities mainly Gazi University TÖMER; and the New Headway Beginner, Elementary, Pre-Intermediate, Intermediate Level course books used almost all over the world in teaching English as a Foreign Language.

2.2 Sampling Procedures

Foreign language teaching books, according to the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages; A1 and A2 for beginner users; for intermediate users, B1 and B2; for advanced users, it is prepared at C1 and C2 levels. While preparing foreign language teaching books, it is necessary to include different or universal cultural elements as well as the cultural elements from which the language is formed. Because language teaching is also a cultural education in a way. However, its limits and the place and balance of national culture and universal culture in language teaching are very important. In this study, it was investigated which cultural elements are included in the textbooks used in teaching Turkish and English as a foreign language. For this, the cultural elements included in A and B (Beginner, Elementary, Pre-Intermediate, Intermediate) levels were determined

and classified according to their themes. While making this classification, previous studies were used and the classification style followed by Okur and Keskin (2013) was adapted to this study.

2.3.1 Sample Size, Power, and Precision

In this part, information will be given on the New Headway Beginner, Elementary, Pre-Intermediate, and Intermediate Level course books, and on Gazi Turkish Teaching Set for Foreigners A1-A2, B1-B2 Level course books, which were included in the study.

New Headway Beginner

The book consists of 14 units related with the following topics; 1st Unit, knowing people, introducing oneself and others; 2nd Unit, countries and cities in the world; 3rd Unit, Jobs and Personal Information; 4th Unit, Family and Friends; 5th Unit, Foods and Beverages, Sports, Languages and Nationalities; 6th Unit; Time and Lifestyles; 7th Unit, Beloved places; 8th Unit, The Place Where We Live; 9th Unit, Birthdays; 10th Unit; Past Tense; 11th Unit, Various Grammar Subjects (capability, modals-proficiency verb, subjunctive and imperative moods); 12th Unit, Foods-beverages and Shopping; 13th Unit, Colors, Clothes, and Present Continuous; 14th Unit, Present Continuous with a Future Meaning; Repeating Question Words, transportation and travel.

New Headway Elementary

The book consists of 14 units related with the following topics; 1st Unit, Meeting people from different countries; 2nd Unit, Elements on Family; 3rd Unit, Jobs of people from different nationalities and the daily lives of these people; 4th Unit, Familial and professional lives of people from different nationalities and their hobbies; 5th Unit, The Living Room and the kitchen and the things in these rooms; 6th Unit, World-famous people and languages; 7th Unit, Things people did in the past, their earnings, and special days of the British Culture; 8th Unit, Past Tense; 9th Unit, Foods; 10th Unit, Comparisons; 11th Unit, External looks of people; 12th Unit, Different languages and different cultures; 13th Unit, Adjectives, adverbs and question types; 14th Unit, Countries and their flags, and the English Breakfast Culture.

New Headway Pre- Intermediate

The book consists of 14 units related with the following topics; 1st Unit, Knowing people, 2nd Unit, Our lifestyles; 3rd Unit, Stories on various topics; 4th Unit, Shopping; 5th Unit, Future events and future tense; 6th Unit, Different Cities from the world; 7th Unit, Famous couples; 8th Unit, Things we have to do, and we do not have to do; 9th Unit, Various countries and cities under the title of ‘Traveling to Other Places’; 10th Unit, Fear from Death; 11th Unit, Things that changes the world; 12th Unit, Dreams and Realities; 13th Unit, Interesting Jobs and People; 14th Unit, Love and leave.

New Headway Intermediate

The book consists of 12 units related with the following topics; 1st Unit, The World; 2nd Unit, Free time; 3rd Unit, Streets and alleys; 4th Unit, Doing the right thing; 5th Unit, Our Changing World; 6th Unit, Various texts under the title of ‘The things that are important for me’; 7th Unit, Passions and Fashion; 8th Unit; Bravery and Courage; 9th Unit, Looking at events from a different angle; 10th Unit, Technology and Our Life; 11th Unit, Seeing is Believing; 12th Unit, Celebrities.

Gazi A1 Turkish Book

The book consists of 6 units related with the following topics; 1st Unit, introducing oneself, introductions, jobs, knowing the environment; 2. Unit, recreational activities, eating, shopping and health; 3rd Unit, Art; 4th Unit, Technical Processes; 5th Unit, asking and giving directions and the cities of Turkey; 6th Unit, special days and celebrations.

Gazi A2 Turkish Book

The book consists of 5 units related with the following topics; 1st Unit, sports, traffic accident news, natural disasters, and some different topics like art and literature, tourism, weather report, etc.; 2nd Unit, letters, notifications, short messages, conversations, departure and arrival hours and destinations of public

transportation, texts about handicraft, recreational activities; 3rd Unit, information on daily events, fairs, social and cultural activities; 4th Unit, emotional bonds in family, social life, working environment; 5th Unit, important values of the Turkish history, scientists who left important marks in history, lifestyles and eating habits of from different cultures and education.

Gazi B1 Turkish Book

The book consists of 5 units related with the following topics; 1st Unit, “It is very easy to be famous (!),” “Virtual Realm,” “The history of the book,” “Superstitions;” 2nd Unit, texts on psychology, personal development and economy; 3rd Unit, texts from different fields like “A Success Story,” “Coffee and Book,” “Road to Fear,” “Our World is Under Threat,” 4th Unit, literature and art; 5th Unit, story and novel.

Gazi B2 Turkish Book

The book consists of 5 units related to the following topics; 1st Unit, “Fine Arts,” “Useful and Harmful: GMO / GMO with useful and harmful ones,” “Archaeology,” “Education of the Highly Intelligent Individuals;” 2nd Unit, “Choosing the Right Job,” “A News Start,” “Establishing Communications”, “The Emperor of the Depths;” 3rd Unit, culture and art; 4th Unit, science, art and literature; 5th Unit, again, art and science.

2.3.2 Measures and Covariates

While obtaining this research data, the main themes in the table below were taken into consideration. These themes were prepared on the basis of ELP (European Language Portfolio) and were previously used in many studies, especially in the work of Okur and Keskin (2013).

Table 1. Cultural Elements Table

Sub-Element	1.DAILY LIFE	2.INTERPERSONAL RELATIONS	3.VALUES AND EDUCATION	4.LITERATURE ART AND MUSIC	5.TRADITIONS AND FOLKLORE	6.SOCIAL LIFE	7.GEOGRAPHY AND LOCATION	8. FOREIGN (UNIVERSAL) CULTURAL ELEMENTS
a	Foods-beverages	People	Values	Literature	Special days and Traditions	Fashion		
b	Meal hours, manners at dining table	Greeting expressions and behaviors	Education	Music	Verbal expressions and verbal traditions	Bans		
c	Official holidays-working hours	Family structures and relations, relations among generations	Language and history Conscious / Love	Art	Behaviors based on religious rules	Applause and good behaviors		
d	Free time activities, hobbies	Relations between political and religious groups	Others	Performance arts	Birth, marriage traditions	Others		
e	Words and structures to be used in dialogues according to age, gender, proximity, social status, and official status	Hospitality-Catering and gifts		Handicraft traditions	Festivals, ceremonies, celebrations			
f	Eating and drinking habits	Others		Others	Dances			
g	Games				Social practices, rituals, superstitions			
h	Sports				Social sciences, practices on the universe and the nature			
i	Music				Others			

3. Findings

3.1. Way of Transmission Cultural Elements: Some of the cultural elements included in the books are tabulated below:

Table 2. Gazi Teaching Turkish to Foreigners Course Book A1 Level

Sub-Element	Way of Transmission Cultural Elements	Place in the Book Level-Page
1a	<i>Döner kebab</i> and other kebab types, and homemade foods like <i>mantı</i> , <i>yaprak sarması</i> (=stuffed leaves), <i>taze fasulye</i> (=fresh beans).	A1-32
1a	Rice pudding, baklava and <i>künefe</i> (=kunafah).	A1-32
1b	We celebrate after prayer and have breakfast altogether.	A1-102
1h	Wrestling, archery ...	A1-28
2a	The name of our daughter is Elif, The name of our son Can	A1-10
2a	First week of Yasemin at her workplace.	A1-104
2b	Have a good business! May it be easy!	A1-38
3c	See Anıtkabir in Ankara	A1-17
4b	Well, "Farewell" from Şebnem Ferah then".	A1-70
5a	Happy October 29, Republic Day!	A1-96
7	We walked nearby the Tuz Gölü (The Salt Lake), we took photos.	A1-90
8	Hans Goldman is a German.	A1-5
8	I am Jamila Anar. I am thirty years old. I am from Kazakhstan	A1-13

Table 3. Gazi Teaching Turkish to Foreigners Course Book A2 Level

Sub-Element	Way of Transmission Cultural Elements	Place in the Book Level-Page
1f	I love pastry like <i>mantı</i> and <i>gözleme</i> (=pancake).	A2-82
2e	... They offered lokum (=Turkish delight) and foamy coffee after dinner.	A2-49
3a	Sabiha Gökçen is the first woman soldier pilot of Turkey and the World.	A2-76
4a	The sixth book of İhsan Oktay Anar, who is one of the master authors of Turkish literature, was placed in on the bookshelves in booksellers in September. The author will take the reader to a new journey with a wide imagination in this book.	A2-8
4c	Neşet Ertaş, who was the famous Turkish poet and singer, was born in 1938 in Kırşehir. UNESCO gave him the reward "Living Cultural Treasury" in 2010.	A2-68
4e	Glass painting, miniature, sand art, knitting, jewelry design ...	A2-46
7	The tour will take place to Kuşadası.	A2-37
7	The Yedigöller National Park in Bolu is like a corner from the paradise ...	A2-88
8	Raw fish, rice, sea food and fresh vegetables are the indispensable elements of the Japanese cuisine ...	A2-80
8	And Newton finds the "Law of Gravity," doesn't he? ...	A2-77

Table 4. Gazi Teaching Turkish to Foreigners Course Book B1 Level

Sub-Element	Way of Transmission Cultural Elements	Place in the Book Level-Page
1a	Lady Aysel baked <i>su böreği</i> (=pasta with cheese and parsley filling), which was her son's favorite dish.	B1-63
1f	My coffee arrived, and it tasted very bitter despite the lokum (=Turkish delight) next to it.	B1-88
2a	" Zeynep , I think you are the rightest person to help me" "Lady Neslihan had three grandsons () named Semih () Esat and Veli and three grandsons named Betül () Zeynep. "	B1-27, 57
2f	My condolences.	B1-10
3b	About this issue, Galatasaray Primary School students organized a science festival, which was named after our famous mathematician Cahit Arf."	B1-26
4a	" Masnawî, " which opens the gates of the mind and the heart, is the most important work of Mevlana.	B1-80
5e	" Kırkpınar Oil Wrestling "	B1-52
5g	Child: Dad, what are you nailing on the door? Dad: Horse shoes , son. Child: Why are you nailing horse shoes? Dad: To protect us from evil. Child: Does that really protect us? Dad: Our ancestors always used to hang horse shoes on their doors , we learnt from them.	B1-17
8	"I was born in 1988, in Freiburg Germany. "	B1-72

Table 5. Gazi Teaching Turkish to Foreigners Course Book B2 Level

Sub-Element	Way of Transmission Cultural Elements	Place in the Book Level-Page
2a	Now, let us know the viewpoints of our specialist doctor Kadir Şafak on this topic.	B2-97
4a	Fuzuli , who is one of the greatest artists of the Classical Turkish Poetry in 16 th Century, is the poet of the Masnawi of Leyla and Mecnun "	B2-6
4a	As far as I learnt from him " The Root of the Rose Bay " was an autobiographical novel. In fact, Muzo in the novel was Muzaffer İzgü himself!	B2-54
4d	"Let our children know Karagöz-Hacivat , which is one of the traditional performance arts of ours, and <i>Meddah</i> (public story-teller) and <i>Orta Oyunu</i> (light comedy).", " Karagöz is a shadow-show. It is performed behind a scene to which light is cast. In this play, Karagöz and Hacivat entertain people with their battle of words." " Hacivat and Karagöz. "	B2-44, 76,77
4e	Copper-work , saddle-maker, pottery, spoon-maker, carpet business... All of these arts require great handicraft, dexterity and mastership.	B2-94
7	The rain, which lasted nearly three hours in Trabzon caused great losses in Sürmene County, and in Beşkøy County, which was wiped out from the maps, caused great loss of lives, destroyed families...	B2-90
8	When the education of highly-intelligent children is considered in the light of the "Multiple Intelligence Theory" of Howard Gardner , this issue may develop in many different areas.	B2-18

Table 6. New Headway Beginner

Sub-Element	Way of Transmission Cultural Elements	Place in the Book Level-Page
1a	He has a big breakfast-coffee, eggs and toast.	BE-44
1e	Hi! Guys, how are you?	BE-22
2a	His name is Simon. He is British.	BE-13
3b	She is a student at university of London.	BE-28
4a	Who was Shakespeare?	BE-66
5a	On Christmas Day we usually all go to my parents' house.	BE-100
7	Toni is from the North of England.	BE-28
8	Her name is Rosely. She is Brazilian.	BE-13

Table 7. New Headway Elementary

Sub-Element	Way of Transmission Cultural Elements	Place in the Book Level-Page
1a	A full English breakfast - Bacon, eggs, toast and marmalade.	EL -111
2d	Margaret Thatcher is the first woman prime minister in Europe.	EL -57
4b	Liverpool's most famous musicians are the Beatles.	EL -79
7	Liverpool is the Britain's second biggest port after London.	EL -79
8	I live in a house in Toluca in Mexico.	EL -16
8	Konnichva!, Bom dia!, Buongiorno!, Privyet!, Sziasztok!, Buenos Dias!, Guten Tag!, Bonjour!	EL-8
8	Visit the pyramids, Fly over the Grand Canyon, See Mount Fuji, See the tulips, Walk along the Great Wall, Watch flamenco dancing, Take photographs of the lions, Sunbathe on Copacabana beach, Walk in Red Square, Visit the Taj Mahal	EL-92

Table 8. New Headway Pre Intermediate

Sub-Element	Way of Transmission Cultural Elements	Place in the Book Level-Page
1h	He has scored fifty goals for Manchester United, and has played for England over thirty times.	PI -58
2a	My name is Robert Palmer.	PI -77
3b	She went to school in the south of England, and studied English at Oxford University.	PI -55
4a	The Big Issue is a magazine sold by homeless people in Britain.	PI-102
5a	In Britain your 18th birthday is important, because it is the birthday when you become an adult.	PI -84
7	River Thames near Oxford	PI -33,49
8	What does she think of living in New York? 'It's very similar to Hong Kong. It's a busy city, very exciting, and people walk very fast!	PI -19

Table 9. New Headway Intermediate

Sub-Element	Way of Transmission Cultural Elements	Place in the Book Level-Page
1h	England has never won the World Cup.	IN-7
2f	In California "How are you?" is considered friendly but here in London some people react with a cold look.	IN-30
3b	In Victorian England, education played a very small role in most children's lives.	IN-32
3b	Problem arose when boys from the different schools went to the Universities of Oxford and Cambridge and wanted to continue playing. (...) Oxford.	IN-58, 91
3c	How long has Elizabeth II been Queen of England?	IN-7
4a	"J.K. Rowling-Harry Potter Book Series," "Joanne Kathleen Rowling, author of the best-selling Harry Potter series of books, was born in 1965, near Bristol, England."	IN-54, 55
5a	My kids are so excited on Christmas Eve, they can't sleep.	IN-48
6d	75% of British households own a car.	IN-17
6d	You have to drive on the left in Britain.	IN-31
7	The idea for Harry came to Rowling while she was travelling by train between Manchester and London.	IN-55
8	Ongota Rangai is a small town near the capital Nairobi.	IN-10

3.2. Comparison of cultural elements in books according to the Cultural Elements Table: Some of the cultural elements included in the books are tabulated as follows:

Table 10. Headway Beginner Course book and Gazi A1 Course Book Culture Transmission Rates

	HEADWAY BEGINNER		GAZI A1	
	f	%	f	%
Daily Life	16	14,41	34	17,5
Relations among People	27	24,32	85	43,8
Values and Education	2	1,80	2	0,01
Literature, Art and Music	3	2,70	5	0,02
Traditions and Folklore	3	2,70	13	6,7
Social Life	2	1,80	14	7,2
Geography and Location	9	8,10	12	6,1
Foreign Cultural Elements	49	44,14	29	14,9
TOTAL	111	100	194	100

According to Table 10, the rate of the cultural elements in Daily Life in Headway Beginner was 14,41%; in Gazi A1 Course Book 17,5%; the rate of the cultural elements in relations among people in Headway Beginner was 24,32%; in Gazi A1 Course Book 43,8%; the rate of the cultural elements in values and education in Headway Beginner was 1,80%; in Gazi A1 Course Book 0,01%; the rate of the cultural elements in literature, art and music in Headway Beginner 2,70%; in Gazi A1 Course Book was 0,02%; the rate of the cultural elements in traditions and folklore in Headway Beginner 2,70%; in Gazi A1 Course Book 6,7%; the rate of the cultural elements in Social Life in Headway Beginner 1,80%; in Gazi A1 Course Book 7,2%; the rate of the cultural elements in Geography and Location in Headway Beginner 8,10%; in Gazi A1 Course Book 6,1%; and when the rate of the cultural elements was considered in Foreign Cultural Element, it was 44,14% in Headway Beginner,

14,9% in Gazi A1 Course Book. Based on these data, it was determined that the local cultural elements in Headway Beginner (aside from values and education, literature, art and music and Geography and Location) were few when compared with the Gazi A1 Course Book; however, it was also determined that the Foreign Cultural Elements were more in Headway Beginner when compared with the Gazi A1 Course Book. When the total of the Cultural Elements were considered, it was understood that the Gazi A1 Course Book included more cultural elements than Headway Beginner.

Table 11. Headway Elementary Course book and Gazi A2 Course Book Cultural elements Numerical Distribution

	HEADWAY ELEMANTARY		GAZİ A2	
	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%
Daily Life	11	12,35	33	34,7
Relations among People	17	19,10	27	28,4
Values and Education	4	4,49	5	5,2
Literature, Art and Music	2	2,24	8	8,4
Traditions and Folklore	3	3,37	5	5,2
Social Life	2	2,24	1	1,05
Geography and Location	2	2,24	11	11,5
Foreign Cultural Elements	48	53,93	5	5,2
TOTAL	89	100	95	100

According to Table 11, the rate of the cultural elements in Daily Life topic in Headway Elementary was 12,35%; and 34,7% in Gazi A2 Course Book; the rate of the cultural elements in Relations among People topic in Headway Elementary was 19,10%; and 28,4% in Gazi A2 Course Book; the rate of the cultural elements in values and education topic in Headway Elementary was 4,49%; and 5,2% in Gazi A2 Course Book; the rate of the cultural elements in literature, art and music topic in Headway Elementary was 2,24%; and 8,4% in Gazi A2 Course Book; the rate of the cultural elements in traditions and folklore topic in Headway Elementary was 3,37%; and 5,2% in Gazi A2 Course Book; the rate of the cultural elements in Social Life in Headway Elementary was 2,24%; and 1,05% in Gazi A2 Course Book; the rate of the cultural elements in Geography and Location in Headway Elementary was 2,24%; and 5,2% in Gazi A2 Course Book; and the rate of Foreign Cultural Elements in Headway Elementary was 53,93%, and 5,2% in Gazi A2 Course Book. Based on this data, it was determined that the local cultural elements in Headway Elementary are less than Gazi A2 Course Book; however, Foreign Cultural Elements in Headway Elementary are more than Gazi A2 Course Book; and Gazi A2 Course Book cared more about the distribution of Cultural Elements than the Headway Elementary and included more cultural elements.

Table 12. Headway Pre-intermediate Course Book and Gazi B1 Course Book Culture Rates

	HEADWAY PREINTERMEDIATE		GAZİ B1	
	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%
Daily Life	28	19,04	8	5,51
Relations among People	29	19,72	59	40,68
Values and Education	3	2,04	6	4,13
Literature, Art and Music	7	4,76	12	8,27
Traditions and Folklore	5	3,40	5	3,44
Social Life	2	1,36	0	0
Geography and Location	5	3,40	14	9,65
Foreign Cultural Elements	68	46,25	41	28,7
TOTAL	147	100	145	100

According to Table 12, the rate of cultural elements in Daily Life topic was 19,04% in Headway Pre-intermediate, and 5,51% in Gazi B1 Course Book; the rate of cultural elements in Relations among People topic in Headway Pre-intermediate was 19,72%; 40,68% in Gazi B1 Course Book; the rate of cultural elements in values and education in Headway Pre-intermediate was 2,04%; 4,13% in Gazi B1 Course Book; the rate of cultural elements in literature, art and music in Headway Pre-intermediate 4,76%; 8,27% in Gazi B1 Course Book; the rate of cultural elements in traditions and folklore topic in Headway Pre-intermediate was 3,40%; 3,44% in Gazi B1 Course Book; the rate of cultural elements in Social Life topic in Headway Pre-intermediate was 1,36; this cultural element was not determined in Gazi B1 Course Book. The rate of cultural elements in Geography and Location topic in Headway Pre-intermediate was 3,40%; 9,65% in Gazi B1 Course Book; the rate of cultural elements in Foreign Cultural Elements topic in Headway Pre-intermediate was 46,25%; 28,7% in Gazi B1 Course Book. Based on these data, it was determined that local cultural elements in Headway Pre-intermediate were more than Gazi B1 Course Book (aside from Daily Life topic); however, foreign cultural elements were more in Headway Pre-intermediate than Gazi B1 Course Book. When the total number of cultural elements was considered it was observed that more cultural elements were included in Headway Pre-intermediate than Gazi B1 Course Book -although with a very little difference.

Table 13. Headway Intermediate Course Book and Gazi B2 Course Book Culture Rates

	HEADWAY INTERMEDIATE		GAZI B2	
	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%
Daily Life	19	10,27	11	8,05
Relations among People	14	7,56	17	12,23
Values and Education	13	7,02	1	0,71
Literature, Art and Music	10	5,40	34	24,4
Traditions and Folklore	9	4,86	0	0
Social Life	8	4,32	0	0
Geography and Location	10	5,40	11	7,91
Foreign Cultural Elements	102	55,13	65	46,7
TOTAL	185	100	139	100

According to Table 13, the rate of cultural elements on Daily Life in Headway Intermediate was 10,27%; 8,05% in Gazi B2 Course Book; the rate of cultural elements on Relations among People in Headway Intermediate was 7,56%; 12,23% in Gazi B2 Course Book; the rate of cultural elements on values and education in Headway Intermediate was 7,02%; 0,71% in Gazi B2 Course Book; the rate of cultural elements on literature, art and music in Headway Intermediate 5,40%; 24,4% in Gazi B2 Course Book; the rate of cultural elements on traditions and folklore in Headway Intermediate was 4,86%; this cultural element was not determined in Gazi B2 Course Book. The rate of cultural elements on Social Life in Headway Intermediate was 1,36%; this cultural element was not determined in Gazi B2 Course Book. The rate of cultural elements on Geography and Location in Headway Intermediate was 3,40%; 9,65% in Gazi B2 Course Book; when the rate of foreign cultural elements was analyzed, it was determined that it was 55,13% in Headway Intermediate; and 46,17% in Gazi B2 Course Book. Based on these data, it was determined that Headway Intermediate included both local cultural Elements (aside from Relations among People and Geography and Location) and foreign cultural elements more than Gazi B2 Course Book. When the total number of cultural elements was analyzed, it was determined that Headway Intermediate included more cultural elements than Gazi B2 Course Book.

4. Result

In this study, the role and importance of culture in foreign language teaching was analyzed and the culture and cultural elements conveyed in the textbooks were examined and presented in detail. The Turkish language teaching set for Gazi foreigners, which is used as a textbook in the centers of Turkish teaching to foreigners of many universities, especially Gazi University TÖMER, and the textbooks of the level of A1-A2, B1-B2, and New Headway Beginner, Elementary, Pre -Intermediate, Intermediate level textbooks were examined and evaluated within the framework of certain criteria in terms of cultural transfer.

In the age we live in, the necessity of cultural transfer in foreign language education is an undeniable phenomenon. During the language learning process, the student should have the experience of getting to know their own cultural values and the values of the target culture closely, thus observing the differences between their own culture and the target culture. In this case, cultural differences can be evaluated unconditionally and without prejudice. In other words, with the awareness created by the different functions of common cultural values in different societies, the student will develop his world view and will not perceive values as just "right" or "wrong." Thus, the student will see that the communities in the world have their own cultural systems and realize that the cultural elements in these cultural systems should be evaluated according to the cultural order they are in.

Foreign language learning is an acculturation process. During this process, the student will experience being more tolerant while learning the target language; will take a universal approach to the events and facts he observes and experiences. In foreign language learning, cultural transfer cannot be regarded as a process or phenomenon that can occur spontaneously. Teachers have an important role in this framework, because they are in one-to-one communication with students throughout the education and teaching process. Students need the help of their teachers in the process of realizing their own cultural values. With this awareness, students can have the opportunity to compare their own culture with the culture of the target language. In this way, the transfer of culture in foreign language teaching can be carried out effectively. In this way, it will be ensured that students develop their intercultural communication skills. Being able to view the culture of the target language from an equal distance with its own culture has a great importance and effect in the context of culture transfer. Apart from the aforementioned data, teachers cannot be expected to provide competence on this subject alone; in addition, the course materials should be arranged in accordance with the cultural transfer. Textbooks used in foreign language teaching should be carefully and cautiously selected according to certain criteria for the realization of cultural transfer.

Comparative culture transfer has an important role in foreign language teaching. Not only should the culture of the target language be transferred to the students, the subjects that the student can compare with his / her own culture should be taken into consideration. If the student is exposed to the target culture values excessively, the student will not be able to assimilate the subject as he / she cannot make a comparison even if he / she grasps the culture structure in which the target language is used. This situation will adversely affect the transfer of culture. In this context, while selecting the textbooks and the texts they contain, in order for the transfer of culture to take place properly, the source culture and the universal cultural elements should be presented together, as well as the data of the target culture, and student comparison should be provided (Soyşekerçi, 2015).

When Gazi A1-A2, B1-B2 level textbooks were examined in terms of cultural transfer, it was seen that Turkish culture, which is the target culture, was presented to students with different aspects, and it was found to be able to provide success in conveying Turkish culture to the student population that it aims to teach Turkish. Although this situation is appropriate in terms of cultural transfer, when it is considered in terms of intercultural communication, it is revealed that there are some deficiencies that will affect the student's acquisition of intercultural communicative competence and cultural awareness. When the textbooks at New Headway Beginner, Elementary, Pre-Intermediate, Intermediate levels are examined in terms of cultural transfer, it is seen that the elements of British culture are given less than the universal cultural elements. This situation may benefit students in intercultural communication, but it will create deficiencies in gaining cultural awareness. Because in

order for students to develop their cultural awareness skills, they need to know the elements of the target culture well. Thus, it can be said that there is no balanced distribution of the target culture and elements of universal culture in the textbooks written by British and Turkish authors.

Similar to the result of this study, Yılmaz (2012) examined the Turkish New Hittite series textbooks for foreigners in terms of cultural transfer, it has been determined that the books contain many elements in which the target culture of Turkish culture is presented to students with different aspects and that it aims to teach Turkish in this way, and that it can provide success in conveying Turkish culture to the student mass. On the other hand, Okur and Keskin (2013), in their study evaluating the Istanbul Turkish Teaching Set for Foreigners in terms of cultural elements, focused more on the number of cultural elements different from this study, found that cultural elements were used less in basic level textbooks, and these elements were included more although it is given, it has the opinion that it should benefit more from cultural elements. The results of his master's thesis study by Lappalainen (2011), in which he examined the transfer of American culture in foreign language textbooks, are consistent with the results of this study. As a result of his study, he found that textbooks do not fully support the principles of intercultural learning and teaching, that American culture is very little compared to other cultures. Karababa and Taşkın (2012), in their study, in which the textbooks used in teaching Turkish as a foreign language were evaluated within the framework of teachers' views, focused on the visuality and themes in the books, unlike this study. As a result of the research, it was found that the New Hittite Turkish textbooks for foreigners are sufficient in terms of visuality and the texts provide integrity; it has been determined that the texts in the books provide integrity with the unit themes. The result of the study of Shin and his friends (2011) examining the reflection of the culture in English teaching textbooks is completely opposite to the result of this study. According to the research, although the cultural dimensions of each textbook are proportionally different, it has emerged that the local cultural content dominates most of the textbooks. Again, in the study of Rajabi and Ketabi (2012) on cultural elements in English textbooks, which do not coincide with the results presented in this study, the findings of the investigated studies reveal that English teaching has become more local in many countries. Kutlu (2012), in his study examining the transfer of culture in Turkish teaching textbooks to foreigners in the example of the Turkish Teaching Set for Gazi Foreigners, thinks that the total number of cultural elements is low, unlike this study. Özişik (2004), in his master's thesis, in which he examined cultural elements in New Headway English textbooks, thinks that these books are successful in cultural transfer. Soyşekerci (2015) examined cultural elements in English and Turkish textbooks, and examined the Izmir A2 Textbook and Global English Teaching textbook, which she took as a sample, and reached similar results with this research. According to the research, when the Izmir A2 Textbook is examined in terms of cultural transfer, it is seen that the target culture, the Turkish culture, contains many elements that are presented to students with different aspects, and the source culture and universal culture elements do not take place in Izmir as much as in the Global; when considered in terms of intercultural communication, it is revealed that there are some deficiencies that will affect the student's acquisition of intercultural communicative competence and cultural awareness. Çelik and Erbay (2013), in their analysis of cultural perspectives in English textbooks in Turkey, the studied language training series, although it has found that European-oriented though students' cultural perspectives include different cultural elements that may help to expand. Abdullah and Chandran (2009) made the following determination in their research, which does not coincide with the result of this study: in many countries, the teaching of English is becoming much more localized, integrating local flavors with those of the target culture. The use of local characters, places, and issues as the content for textbooks is subtly interspersed with the cultural contexts of English-speaking countries. This is a necessity as language could not be totally divorced from culture (Abdullah & Chandran, 2009: 17). Tajeddin and Teimournezhad (2015), in their study examining the presentation of local and universal cultural elements in English teaching textbooks, concluded that a balance should be established between local and universal elements in the textbooks, as we emphasized in our research. In his study, Yuen (2011) analyzed the cultural content in two textbooks used in teaching English by Hong Kong students, and found that the cultural content given in these textbooks was mainly related to English-speaking countries, that is, universal cultural elements.

As a result, it can be said that while cultural elements are given in foreign language textbooks, there should be a proportional balance between local cultural elements and universal cultural elements. Because intercultural

transfer is very important in today's language teaching. Teachers have a great responsibility in this regard. In this context, foreign language students should be told first of all that there is not a single thought and life system in the world, but that there are different cultural groups and lifestyles. The point to be considered here should be to make students compare these different cultural groups and lifestyles with their own way of life and thinking, that is, with their own culture. In Choudhury (2014), he argues that foreign language classes should be taught English to students in connection with their own culture. Thus, students can demonstrate the correct cultural awareness behavior. Writers who prepare foreign language textbooks should also have this point of view; students should be able to find the opportunity to compare the target culture with different cultural values in the books.

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